

Self-Concept as a Correlate of Academic Achievement of Students in English Language in Public Secondary Schools in Nnewi Education Zone, Anambra State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT: Self concept is a fundamental aspect of one's life which facilitates the motivation that comes from within.. This study examined self-concept as correlates of academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone. The study was guided by three research questions and one hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlation research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of 8,150 SS2 students in the 48 public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone. Multi-stage random sampling procedure was used to draw a sample size of 782 students. The instruments for data collection were Self Concept Questionnaire (SCQ) and SS2 Students Achievements Scores (SAS) in English Language. The instruments were validated by experts and the consistency of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha reliability index. Self Concept Questionnaire (SCQ) yielded an aggregate of 0.79 coefficient which was considered fit for the study. The administration of the instruments were done through the direct method approach with the help of four research assistants. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was utilized for data analysis. The p-value was used to determine the relationship of the variables at 0.05 level of significance for the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that self concept has a high positive and significant relationship on academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone. The study recommended amongst others that Anambra State Post Primary School Service Commission should encourage the principals and teachers to educate the students on the essence of self concept in the learning of English Language to enable them achieve a successful academic purpose.

KEYWORDS: Self-concept, Academic Achievement, English Language and Public Secondary Schools.

INTRODUCTION

The desire for qualitative education remains a major concern to educators, scholars, stakeholders and all lovers of education. Primary efforts of teachers, school counsellors, school administrators and all those involved in the process of teaching and learning are usually geared towards enhanced academic achievement. Educators at different levels, especially the secondary schools, ensure effective approaches to motivate students' desires and willingness to learn for improved academic achievements. This helps in evaluating students' record success in the learning processes. Teachers work hard to ensure quality instructional delivery for improved performances and increased academic achievement of the students.

Academic achievement can be seen as the extent at which the students recorded success in their pursuit of learning. According to Narad and Abdullah (2016), academic achievement can be defined as the knowledge gained after assessment has been done by a teacher to meet educational goals as enshrined in the curriculum for a fixed period of time. Zhou and Siti (2022), saw academic achievement as a direct manifestation of learning effectiveness and a valid indicator to evaluate the effectiveness of teaching and learning, as well as the overall development of students. Teachers' and learners' efforts towards positive learning outcomes can reflect on academic achievement. Scholars agreed that students' academic achievement is a 'net result' of their cognitive and non-cognitive attributes (Lee and Stankov, 2016).

Positive records of academic achievement can be a motivator for continuing growth in academics and some related school activities for the present and future days. Academic achievement shows profound impact on personal, professional and societal development which can also foster opportunities for career advancement, discipline and resilience to the older and younger generations (Zhou and Siti, 2022). Considering the need for improved academic achievement of students especially in secondary schools, it is anticipated that best performances can be enhanced through integration of quality teaching measures with self concept of students.

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In other words, students' belief about themselves as learners and willingness to handle academic tasks could correlate with their academic achievement.

Self-concept can be a reflection on how someone sees oneself and having a sense of worth and confidence. Self-concept can be a source of strength and energy to the individual at different stages of growth. Carl Rogers a renowned psychologist in 1940s - 1950s opined self-concept to portray three distinct components comprising self image, self esteem and the ideal self. Carl also argued that these components are not always aligned with reality, emphasizing that they could be congruent or incongruent depending on the individual. In Carl's view, self concept is said to be congruent when it is aligned with reality and incongruent when there exists a mismatch between what one wishes and the real situation.

Self concept is a fundamental aspect of one's life which is peculiar to everyone. It evolves or changes over time depending on the individual's frequent experiences of new things, environment, interactions and maturity. According to Anyadubalu, Nwokolo and Chibu (2025), self-concept is a contentious psychological topic that is unstable and may affect, grow, or alter in diverse ways throughout time. It can be positive at a time boosting confidence, self worth and also yielding good results through determination. However, it may be negative at another time, being identified with feelings of doubt and unbelief in one's capabilities and strength. Therefore, students ought to be encouraged to maintain a positive self-concept for efficiency in abilities and self worth.

Students with a positive self-concept may likely develop internal motivation to strive for excellence in studies rather than being indifferent and passive (Okonkwo, Okafor-agbala and Obikezie, 2022). Self concept appears crucial in the lives and growing up of individuals, especially in students. Self-concept provides the necessary framework for parents and teachers to encourage their wards to build themselves (Obialor, Onyemakara, Okeke and Nwankwo, 2023). This is to say that self-concept could encourage students in schooling and as well relates to motivation of learning desires for willingness in academic activities which leads to greater academic success.

Self concept shows how someone thinks, evaluates or perceives oneself. It reflects the personal knowledge of who we are, encompassing our thoughts and feelings; physically, personally and socially. (Okafor, Obialor and Osuafor, 2020). This implies that self-concept can help the students to develop the willingness for personal growth in thoughts and career. Students could cultivate the zeal for pursuit of excellence in academics. It helps students to build up capabilities and determinations for success in school. Jackson (2022), affirmed that self-concept includes the knowledge of how the individual behave, capabilities and individual characteristics. Students who have self concept tend to approach studies with great confidence and motivation, which can lead to greater academic outcomes.

On the other hand, negative self-perceptions might hinder their ability to fully engage in their educational pursuits and academic achievement (Obialor, Onyemakara, Okeke, Nwankwo, 2023). In other words, students' perception of their own abilities can often play a vital role in determining their academic success, achievement and self actualization. Academic achievement of students evidenced with high grades or academic recognition can positively correlate with self concept and by extension boosting the student's resilience and perseverance. In the context of educational development, Obialor, Onyemakara, Okeke, Nwankwo (2023), asserted that a crucial interplay exists between academic achievement and self-concept. This assertion ponders the researcher, if it can be obtainable in English Language of public secondary secondary school students in Nnewi Education Zone.

In Nigeria, English Language is the lingual franca as it is commonly used among people of different native languages as a general means of communication. Currently at Nnewi, there are vast and fast growing business enterprises going on in the region, especially the motor and motorcycle spare parts dealers. People of diverse speaking languages coming over for business ventures and English Language at this point becomes crucial for effective means of communication and business interactions. In university education, courses cannot be offered for admission without a credit pass in English Language. It becomes necessary to lay much emphasis on the academic achievement of students in English Language especially for those who intend to continue with further education.

It has been noted that some students in Anambra State still experience difficulties in learning English Language, the improved contents and learning experiences. Zalmon and Wonu (2017), opined that we need nothing short of good academic achievement in English Language and Mathematics to attain the Nigeria National Development Aspiration by the year 2030. The NECO Annual Report (2022), revealed that candidates who sat for the Year 2021 SSCE examination in Anambra State and recorded Credit Pass in Mathematics and English Language were 66.67%. This record shows moderate achievement scores. However, the annual record of (2023), revealed that candidates who sat for the SSCE examination and recorded credit pass in English Language were 47.05% which indicated a decrease and low achievement scores. The WASSCE Annual Report (2023), shows the general performance of candidates in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE); in Year 2022, out of 271,642 candidates who sat for the examination, a total of 86,926 (32%) candidates obtained credits in five subjects and above including English Language and Mathematics while in Year 2023, out of 265,819 candidates who sat for the West African Senior School Certificate Examination, only 88,252 (33.2%) scored five credits in Mathematics, English Language and any three other subjects which show only a slim difference.

These academic records call for concern. The need for greater academic achievement especially in English Language becomes essential in the public secondary schools in Nnewi education zone. This situation necessitates the study, the researcher was motivated

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to examine the relationship between self concept and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study examined self-concept as correlates academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Research Question

The research questions below guided the study:

1. What are the self-concept scores of Public Secondary School Students in Nnewi Education Zone.
2. What are the English Language academic achievement scores of Public Secondary School Students in Nnewi Education Zone.
3. What is the relationship between the self concept and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone?

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis below was formulated for the study and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary school in Nnewi Education Zone.

METHODS

Correlation research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of 8,150 senior secondary school II (SS2) students in the 48 Public Secondary Schools in Nnewi Education Zone. The zone is made up of 4 Local Government Areas; namely: Ekwusigo, Ihiala, Nnewi North and Nnewi South Local Government Areas. Multi-stage random sampling procedure was used to draw 10% of 8,150 students from the entire population, representing the sample size of the study. The instruments for data collection were Self Concept Questionnaire (SCQ) and SS2 Students Achievements Scores (SAS) in English Language. The questionnaire was structured with each item assigned a four point scale of: Strongly Agree (SA); Agree (A); Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD), and corresponding values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was validated by experts in the field and considered fit for the study. The internal consistency of the items was obtained using Cronbach alpha which yielded an aggregate reliability coefficient of 0.79. The researcher administered the copies of the instrument directly to the respondents involving four research assistants. Out of the 815 copies administered to the respondents, a total of 782 copies representing 96% were properly completed, successfully retrieved and used for data analysis. The percentage correlation among students' self concept scores and English Language achievement scores were ascertained using the scores of SS2 students. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation coefficient (r) was used to answer the research questions and hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The coefficient (r) between 0.0 - 0.40 yielded a low positive relationship, between 0.41 - 0.60 yielded a moderate positive relationship, between 0.61 - 0.80 yielded a high positive relationship and between 0.81 - 1.00 yielded a very high substantial positive relationship. In testing the hypotheses the decision rules that when p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis were rejected, (there is a significant relationship). Otherwise, where the p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was not rejected (there is no significant relationship). Data analysis was computed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences Version 23 (SPSS, 2023).

RESULTS

Research Question One. What are the self concept scores of public secondary school students in Nnewi Education Zone?

Table 1: Range of scores on self concept of public secondary school students in Nnewi Education Zone.

Range of Scores	N	%	Remarks
26 - 44	338	43.2	Low self concept
45 - 78	444	56.8	High self concept

Table 1 shows that a total number of 338 students being 43.2% of the respondents with the scores ranging from 26 to 44 reported of having low self concept while 444 students representing 56.8% of the respondents with the scores ranging from 45 to 78 reported of having high self concept in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Research Question Two. What are the academic achievement scores of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone?

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Table 2: Range of scores on academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary school students in Nnewi Education Zone.

Range of Scores	N	%	Remarks
0 - 39	31	4.0	Poor Achievement
40 - 49	422	54.0	Fair Achievement
50 - 69	306	39.0	Good Achievement
70 - 100	23	3.0	Very Good Achievement

Table 2 shows that a total number of 31 students being 4.0% of the respondents with the scores ranging from 0 to 39, reported poor academic achievement in English Language. Also 422 students representing 54.0% of the respondents with the scores ranging from 40 to 49, reported fair academic achievement in English Language and 306 students representing 39.0% of the respondents with the scores ranging from 59 to 69, reported good academic achievement in English Language. Meanwhile, 23 students representing 3.0% of the respondents with scores ranging from 70 to 100, reported very good academic achievement in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Research Question Three. What is the relationship between the self concept and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone?

Table 3: Pearson (r) correlation on the relationship between self concept and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone

Source of Variation	N	r	Remarks
Self Concept	782	.691	High Positive Relationship
Academic Achievement			

Results in Table 3 showed that Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of 0.691 was obtained. With reference to the interpretation guide by Okoye (2015), 0.691 is between 0.61 and 0.80 showing a high positive relationship. This indicates that there is a high positive relationship existing between self concept and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Null Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Table 4: Test of significance of Pearson's correlation between self concept and academic achievement of students in English Language public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Source of Variation	N	r	P-value	Remarks
Self Concept	782	.691	0.000	*Significant
Academic Achievement				

Analysis in Table 4 showed that there is a significant relationship between self concept and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone. The calculated r (0.691) had a P- value of 0.000 less than 0.05 level of significance level ($0.00 < 0.05$). The null hypothesis one, which states that there is no significant relationship between self concept and academic achievement of students in English Language was therefore rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings indicated that the majority of the students in Nnewi Education Zone have self concept in themselves. This report implied that the larger number of students in the zone maintains a strong internal representation of oneself, which boosts personal capabilities and characteristics for strengthening of self confidence and self worth. These self dispositions support the students in making firm decisions that enable them to progress successfully in their academic process. It also supports the students in getting more focus on academic involvements and activities for increased academic achievement. The finding is in line with Okonkwo, Okafor-agbala and Obikezie (2022), who revealed that self-concept has a high positive relationship with academic achievement of students. Self-concept helps learners to develop internal motivation that supports effective learning. The findings of this study also agreed with Nwosu and Samuel (2022), who concurred that self concept has a high predictive value on academic achievement of students. In other words, self concept helps the students to build up the willingness to study and achieve best results.

The findings also indicated that 43.2% of the students in the zone have low self concept. This showed that there are still some students in the Nnewi Education Zone who do not have a strong internal representation of oneself or the motivation that comes from

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within. This low self concept could probably be the reason for poor academic achievement, due to lack of self motivation towards learning. Basically, as students, the personal knowledge of who they are and what they intend to become help in the definition of focus and target academically. Thus, low self concept dwarfs the ability to make such academic choices. This finding agreed with Obialor, Onyemakara, Okeke, Nwankwo (2023), who emphasized lack of self concept hinders successful academic achievement of students. This implies that students who lack self concept cannot perform well in schools nor record good academic achievement.

The findings of this study also reported that the majority of the students recorded fair performances resulting in low academic achievement in English Language. This report is in line with the NECO Annual Report (2022), which revealed that candidates who sat for the Year 2021 SSCE examination in Anambra State and recorded credit pass in Mathematics and English Language were 66.67%. However, this result was reported as a low achievement record. The findings also agreed with the WASSCE Annual Report (2023), which revealed that the general performance of candidates in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE); in the year 2022 & 2023 and obtained credit pass in Mathematics and English Language were 32.0% and 33.2% respectively. This also clearly indicated a low academic achievement score. Improved efforts are expected from the principals and teachers in Anambra State, especially Nnewi Education Zone towards motivating and stimulating interests of the students to learn. The focus will be aimed at increasing the academic achievement of the students in English Language.

Further findings of this study also indicated that 3.0% of the students in the zone recorded very good achievement while 39.0% recorded fair achievement scores. Though the report revealed fair academic achievement, there could still be records of greater achievement scores of the students; if improved strategies and enhanced approaches are adopted in teaching and learning of the English Language. Contrarily, it could still turn out otherwise if the strategies and measures taken to improve the students' academic achievement were unproductive. This finding concurred with Nwachukwu (2022), who noted that one of the major challenges of teaching and learning for improved academic achievement is how to motivate and encourage the students to learn. Ojukwu (2017), in the study observed that public secondary schools in Anambra State still face significant challenges regarding students' academic achievement in English Language. Obviously, most of the schools still struggle to meet up with the standard academic achievement level. The lesser percentage of the students representing 42.0% indicated that public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone still face challenges in learning the English Language. Therefore, the need for an improved teaching and learning process on the subject becomes essential.

The findings also showed a high positive relationship existing between self concept and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone. This result revealed that having a sense of positive self worth and confidence helps to stimulate students' desire for learning. These students can said to be self motivated which could help them perform better in their studies, leading to greater academic achievement. The relationship implies that students who hold strong belief and feelings about themselves towards learning, record successful academic achievement in English Language. This finding is in line with Okonkwo, Okafor-agbala and Obikezie (2022), who noted a significant relationship between self concept and cognitive development of students and recommended increased efforts in motivating students' sense of self worth and purpose towards learning. This indicates that students who possess self concept could build up self worth that helps them in recording increased academic achievement. The study also recommended sufficient attention to academic programs and learning contents for increased achievement records.

Further findings of the study also indicated that there is a significant relationship between self concept and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary school in Nnewi Education Zone. Self concept could enable the students to make firm decisions, take positive steps and pursue self determined academic goals. This finding concurred with Nwosu and Samuel (2022), who noted that self concept to significantly predict students' academic achievement and study recommended that achievement motivation and self-concept should be enhanced by using appropriate teaching and counselling strategies. Similarly, the findings of Obialor, Onyemakara, Okeke and Nwankwo (2023), also agreed to this finding. Their study revealed a moderate positive and significant relationship between secondary school students' self-concept and their academic achievement. The study laid much emphasis on Basic Science while this study correlated English Language and they had similar findings. This indicated that self concept is quite essential to be built up in the students of public secondary schools in Anambra State across the education zones, both high and low achieving students in order to equip and support them in learning for increased academic achievement.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it was concluded that self concept correlates academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone. Self-concept has a significant and high positive relationship with academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

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1. Guidance and Counsellors should encourage the students to cultivate a strong self concept that will help them to maintain firm academic decisions and get focused on learning outcomes.
2. The State Post Primary School Service Commission should also encourage the principals and teachers to educate the students on the need for self concept which motivates completion of every academic cycle, in their educational pursuit.

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